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The cellular state as a basic framework in disease.

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Case study 1: Reduction of proliferation and a switch in cellular state to terminally differentiated foam cell in atherogenic CVD.

Case study 2: IL-7 based switch in cellular state during transition from migration to homing and colonization in brain metastasis: IL-7R.